

Storm surge simulations and open-source flow solvers

Giordano Lipari

Watermotion | Waterbeweging

International Symposium on Shallow Flows

28 June 2017

The context of storm-surges simulations

Society

Floods can injure, kill, damage and destroy

Venice, St Mark's Basilica, ca. 1100

Challenges in collaborative decision-making

Numerical modelling increasingly becomes a standard tool for decision support ...

Modelling increasingly is imposed on public sector organizations through legislation and recommendations by academia and engineering consultants

At the same time ... tools for managing quality control and knowledge are lagging behind these expectations ... (Convenor's call for the iEMSs Conference 2016)

Risk-based approach to decision-making and valuations

Risk = hazard × damage

Storm-surge simulations are instrumental to both factors of risk

Insurance value of mistakes and errors in modelling and implementation

Modelling

Modelling and simulation

*Broadly defined, **modelling** is a method for organizing knowledge accumulated through observation or deduced from underlying principles, while **simulation** refers to a method for implementing a model over time* (Paul C. Etter)

The knowledge chain

Physical modelling Principles and investigations
Mathematical formulation Quantification, calculus/analysis
Mathematical solution Numerics, algebra, algorithms
Software implementation Coding
Software utilization Steering, execution, information retrieval

Model quality assurance

Verification Making sure that **the equations are solved right**
Validation Making sure that **the right equations** are being solved
Calibration Seeking agreement with specific evidence

Everything should be made as simple as possible, but not simpler

Evaluation of errors — some examples

Numerical modelling

Mistakes Conceptual and implementation flaws

Acknowledged errors Discretisation of domains and equations, ...

Software testing Evidence versus expectation

PASS	XPASS
FAIL	XFAIL

Confusion matrix Sampling versus evidence

True positive	False positives
False negative	True negatives

Errors of execution (aviation)

Commission Doing what you ought not

Omission Not doing what you ought

Slips Minor errors

Lapses Distraction, incomplete tasks, omitted steps

Mistakes Actions conform to an inadequate plan

Violations Deviation from safe procedures, standards or rules

Open-sourceness

Definition 1. Free redistribution — 2. Source code — 3. Derived works — 4. integrity of the author's source code — 5. No discrimination against persons or groups — 6. No discrimination against fields of endeavor — 7. Distribution of license — 8. License must not be specific to a product — 9. License must not restrict other software — 10. License must be technology-neutral (www.opensource.org)

Economy

Also supported by, and spawning, business models and collective investments
Negotiating the market/marketing dilemma

Ecosystem

The anthouse — Scientist \neq developer \neq 'power user' \neq generalistic user \neq ...
The 'as is' clause — the responsibility issue
Flavours, tools, idols, ...
Fora, distributed intelligence and ignorance, ...
Here, power-user approach

Analytical solutions
for storm tide codes

One-dimensional linearized mass and momentum conservation

$$\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial t} = -H \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = -g \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x} - \lambda u + \frac{\mathcal{F}_0}{H}$$

λ friction coefficient [1/s]

H basin depth [m]

$\mathcal{F}_0 = \tau_s / \rho_w$ squared friction velocity [m^2/s^2]

Coastal Engineering 46 (2002) 213–231

**Coastal
Engineering**

An International Journal for Coastal
Estuarine and Offshore Engineering

www.elsevier.com/locate/coastaleng

Analytical solutions for storm tide codes

Rodney J. Sobey*

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of California, 539 Dues Hall, Berkeley, CA 94720, USA

Received 29 August 2001; received in revised form 24 May 2002; accepted 4 June 2002

Abstract

A sequence of analytical solutions explore aspects of response patterns expected from numerical codes for storm tides in one- and two-dimensional basins. Complete analytical details of the solutions are provided, together with specific suggestions for an associated set of analytical benchmark tests. Illustrations of predicted response patterns provide the basis for a discussion of many significant physical aspects and their representation in discrete numerical codes.

© 2002 Elsevier Science B.V. All rights reserved.

Here, wind forcing on a partially open basin

Sobey's analytical solution ◦ Surge on a partially open basin

Sobey's analytical solution ◦ Sudden uniform steady wind on a partially open basin

Sobey's analytical solution ◦ Sudden uniform steady wind on a partially open basin

Basin length L and modes

$$\beta_n = \left(n - \frac{1}{2}\right) \frac{\pi}{L}$$
$$X_n = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin \beta_n x \quad Y_n = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \cos \beta_n x$$
$$\hat{f}_n = -\frac{\mathcal{F}_0}{gH} \int_0^L x X_n(x) dx \quad \hat{g}_n = \mathcal{F}_0 \int_0^L Y_n(x) dx$$

Long-wave dispersion relationship — friction and oscillations

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{gH\beta_n^2 - \lambda^2/4}$$

(also telling whether/which oscillations can live on a discrete mesh, hence $\Delta x \Rightarrow \Delta t$)

Water level and depth-averaged velocity — time- and space-varying

$$\eta(x, t) = \frac{\mathcal{F}_0}{gH} x + e^{-\frac{\lambda}{2}t} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\cos \omega_n t + \frac{\lambda}{2} \frac{\sin \omega_n t}{\omega_n} \right) \hat{f}_n X_n(x)$$
$$u(x, t) = e^{-\frac{\lambda}{2}t} \frac{1}{H} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin \omega_n t}{\omega_n} \hat{g}_n Y_n(x)$$

Sobey's analytical solution ◦ Travelling wind pulse on a partially open basin

Numerical solutions with “open-source” solvers

Tunables of a flow solver — linearizing the equations

Adcirc
(Advanced Circulation)
52.30.13
FEM

D-Flow FM
(Flexible Mesh)
1.1.116
FVM

Telemac
7.2.1
FEM

```
0 ! NOLIBF
0 ! NOLIFA
0 ! NOLICA
0 ! NOLICAT
... ! TAU
... ! TAUO
```

```
AdvectType = 0
Lincontin = 1
Umodlin = 1
UnifFricCoefLin = ...
Vicouv = 0
Vicoww = 0
+ code tweak
```

```
ADVECTION = NO
DIFFUSION OF VELOCITY = NO
LINEARIZED PROPAGATION = YES
MEAN DEPTH FOR LINEARIZATION
LAW OF BOTTOM FRICTION = 1
FRICTION COEFFICIENT = ...
TURBULENCE MODEL = 1
VELOCITY DIFFUSIVITY = 0.
```

Plus wind forcing, time-marching schemes, shape functions, observation points, ...

Test case

$$\lambda = 0$$

means no friction

The bed shear stress term vanishes

And the surge and heave are periodic

Δt is such that all oscillations supported by the grid are resolved
'Supported' and 'live' means that the Nyquist criterion holds
The solver is not triaged beyond the possible

detail ◦ A ◦ frictionless motion ◦ water level ◦ mid basin

detail ◦ A ◦ frictionless motion ◦ water level ◦ all basin

detail ◦ D ◦ frictionless motion ◦ water level ◦ mid basin

detail ◦ D ◦ frictionless motion ◦ water level ◦ all basin

detail ◦ T ◦ frictionless motion ◦ water level ◦ mid basin

detail ○ T ○ frictionless motion ○ water level ○ all basin

detail ◦ A ◦ frictionless motion ◦ d/a velocity ◦ mid basin

detail ◦ A ◦ frictionless motion ◦ d/a velocity ◦ all basin

detail ◦ D ◦ frictionless motion ◦ d/a velocity ◦ mid basin

detail ◦ D ◦ frictionless motion ◦ d/a velocity ◦ all basin

detail ◦ T ◦ frictionless motion ◦ d/a velocity ◦ mid basin

detail ◦ T ◦ frictionless motion ◦ d/a velocity ◦ all basin

Test case

$$\lambda \neq 0$$

Damped oscillations

Surge levels at the downwind end

Depth-averaged velocity at the open boundary

A, D, T ◦ time history ◦ downwind end ◦ surge height

detail ◦ A ◦ time history ◦ downwind end ◦ surge height

detail ◦ T ◦ time history ◦ downwind end ◦ surge height

A, D, T \circ time history \circ open boundary \circ mass exchange

detail ◦ D ◦ time history ◦ open boundary ◦ mass exchange

detail ◦ T ◦ time history ◦ open boundary ◦ mass exchange

Error regularity
Convergence analysis

mesh and time-step convergence

mesh and time-step convergence

mesh and time-step convergence

Error regularity and convergence
Time and space has been discretized
Gradients are approximated

Order of convergence, n

If $|N - A| \sim O(\Delta x)^n$

then

$$\frac{|N - A|}{O(\Delta x)^n}$$

is constant

detail ◦ A ◦ data

detail ◦ D ◦ data

detail ◦ T ◦ data

detail ◦ A ◦ mesh and time-step convergence ◦ $\epsilon \sim O(\Delta x)^2$?

detail ◦ D ◦ mesh and time-step convergence ◦ $\epsilon \sim O(\Delta x)^2$?

detail ◦ T ◦ mesh and time-step convergence ◦ $\epsilon \sim O(\Delta x)^2$?

detail ◦ A ◦ Mesh and time-step convergence ◦ $\epsilon \sim O(\Delta x)$?

detail ◦ D ◦ Mesh and time-step convergence ◦ $\epsilon \sim O(\Delta x)$?

detail ◦ T ◦ Mesh and time-step convergence ◦ $\epsilon \sim O(\Delta x)$?

Error regularity

Considering that

- Joint Δx -and- Δt refinement (Nyquist/Courant)
- No advection and diffusion, hence $\eta \sim O(\Delta x)^n \Rightarrow u \sim O(\Delta x)^{n-1}$
- $|N - A|/\Delta x^n$ tests the n -th order of convergence

it appears that

- A, D u , zero-th order η , first order
- T u , first order η , zero-th order

keeping in mind that

- Evidences valid for (subject to) given settings
- Any validation exercise is necessary because no-one is sufficient

Concluding remarks

The independent comparison of storm-surge simulation skills of (open-source) solvers is feasible — Ongoing work

Any validation exercise is necessary because no-one is sufficient — Unsteady and spatially varying flow, energy conservation, time integration

The parameters space to explore for verification is considerable — An insightful journey

Points for attention can be identified — Opportunity for reasoned critique and improved reliability ('feature requests')

Beware disconnecting physical modelling, mathematical formulations and software implementation

Beware false economies (pragmatic modelling)? — Morphology pays the bill...?

Will flow solvers be appified?

Will flow solvers become interchangeable?

In memoriam G.H. Jirka (1944-2010)

Thanks for having me here

Watermotion | Waterbeweging
consultancy · marketing · outreach · research

www.watermotion.eu

www.watertu.be

[@hydrodynamics](https://twitter.com/hydrodynamics)
glnl@gmail.com

